

Witness protection and identity verification, why it is important?

Part 1

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Introduction – addressing the importance

When and where is the true identity of the person the principal component to be verified?

Three instances of interest for such delicate verification:

- I. huge amount of money payout (yellow alert¹),
- II. testimony in a high profile international serious and organized crime ring (red alert),
- III. access to top secret information (green alert).

Part 1 of the importance of identity verification will address some aspects of the perfect crime, that focuses on an actual challenge and explains motives behind such acts. Part 2 will focus more on technical legal structures that should be addressed and solved on a global level.

Part one: money payout (yellow alert)

Within the realm of 2 major financial means providers, the fiat world and the crypto world, each one allows contained wallets and financial value containers to hide stolen assets. The financial system within its branching structure that allows to hold financial assets, has an ocean of possibilities on where and how they are stored. Each money payments or storage provider has its own mechanism of back door bypass system to allow criminal money to have a free flow without detection. Not only for the purpose of crime tax evasion purposes, but also for agencies to conduct cover operations with specific goals to target specific individuals and remain undetected to the public eye.

In most cases, with a forged document, an impostor can always present her or himself at the financial institution showing only the forged document, since there is no centralized system of document verification implemented in financial institutions, both fiat and crypto alike. Even though the money should be made available to the real person, if it is done behind the scenes without real harm to the victim, the severity of identity theft falls under the yellow alert.

Part two: testimony (red alert)

As crime is a global phenomenon and it's world does not distinguish between ethnicity, borders, cultures, morality or any other contained human limitation, to prove international connections of sophisticated systemic money laundering, the person who is directly involved and tied to the events in a scope of a witness, needs either be tempered or intimidated to such extent, that refuses to testify for personal reason. If intimidation method of mind control fails, the next feasible and possible step becomes identity theft and corrupting officials to verify a so called 'copy' of a real person, who will provide a narrative wanted by the crime syndicates in court. Courts in different regimens, do not

¹ Alerts are defined in terms of severity status: red – extreme importance, yellow – mediocre importance, green – not severe importance

have any digital verifiable method to validate a person, they only rely on the document provided by the person or the escort done by the police. The testimony of a real person in court cases is of the essence and the most important instance, where true identity of the person taking an oath is of key importance to convict the criminals responsible of the international crime syndicate.

Each member state has its own legal framework of post delivery connected to registered permanent address. However, post officials can be compromised along with digital systems. In Slovenia for example, all foreign post first passes through a common center in one centralized warehouse. If post is of interest of the criminal syndicate, the letter can be removed from the center and another letter produced by the local authorities, where signature is required. The foreign entity therefore believes, that the person to whom the letter was sent, was the actual recipient of the sent information. If the person of interest, living in a different state, is unaware of the event, the criminal syndicate using the official police and embassy networks, issuing a forged identity document, gives a guarantee that the falsely verified person, is the person, to whom the invitation was being sent. Such instance of the verification of the real person falls under red alert, because in a case a different person testifies, the whole investigation falls apart and the criminals, who are the shame of humanity, are let free to walk the streets, continuing in conducting criminal activities.

Part three: access to information (green alert)

The principal difference to have access to information is whether the documentation is in digital or physical form, both strictly tight to physical access control to either a device or a piece of archived document. Access control can be implemented on several layers of physical access and the criticality of personal verification can be applied systemically on the biological characteristics of a human body that cannot be tempered or hacked, meaning, that even if digital identity on social networks is compromised, when physical access control is in place, no digitally faked evidence can grant access without the real person to be present at a predefined place of interest. Such methods can only be implemented in high security settings, taking into account the building's architecture as well as digital access control to enter specific rooms or settings of the building. Even though, access is granted on only need to know basis, tempering with well defined security protocol can be a mission impossible, consequently, falling into the green security alert category.

How is it possible to achieve such a perfect crime in 21st century?

What if, throughout the investigation process done in a different member state, it's shown that the verified legal entity, like the police, for the purpose of a criminal investigations, makes use of the immunity from SAR reporting granted by the AML directive, to actually commit a crime? Not only abusing the taxpayers money, but with criminal intent, purposefully sabotaging the truth, with the use of legal entities and their personnel of a specific corrupt state, to protect the real criminals, bypassing persecution with the excuse of a criminal investigation?

The EU AML directives throughout its applicative framework, allow obliged entities to not report entities on AML scope limitation mandated by the directive. Meaning, for the purposes of covert operations or investigations, private non profit or for profit entities can rely on bank secrecy limitations to not reveal information without a court order, unless the bank has illegal leaks or the system gets hacked. When a legal entity is registered within the scope of criminal investigations, the bank is not mandated to report SAR reports within the defined legal framework, since the transactions are executed based on trust of the legal proceedings. To describe a perfect crime, the

communication channels of the victim have to be tempered with. To elaborate on the digital levels of abuse, it is necessary to understand primary identity verification components:

- I. Digital signature
- II. E-mail communication
- III. Telephone number

To elaborate on the statement above, if the crime syndicate infiltrated within the police force, abuses a digital signature of a trusted individual based on their past experiences and trust verifications, such legal entities can illegally obtain a bank card with only a digitally signed document done by the abused individual. In a small corrupt state within the European Union, to obtain a digital signature, a separate card reader for security purposes is not needed, only a password protected file that gets activated by the person who receives the e-mail with a verification number and a separate protected envelope sent by post. Once the file is activated and imported into the browser or any other software of interest, such device officially becomes that person. In legal terms imposed by the digital signature laws, no channels are obliged to keep track and record of the use of the digital signature. Such task is left to the digital signature holder. In other words, if a file ever gets stolen by the crime syndicate, a person abused can never obtain any proof of digital traces, meaning, the criminals have free access to forge and obtain anything they want, using that person's identity. Digitally signed documents become officially verified documents, even though the real person has never granted any access to them.

Next point to clarify, is the use of digital communication. To contact an individual, the world accepts two key communication methods, a phone number and an e-mail address. Manipulation and abuse techniques will be elaborated accordingly.

First, to step up security measures to protect free provider's e-mail accounts (gmail, protonmail, etc), one can use a security key produced by different providers. Login access to an e-mail is only granted with the use of a security key, because password can easily be compromised with installing a keylogger on the victim's computer. A keylogger is a malicious software infiltrated into the system, that is hard to detect without computer forensics knowledge, that sends keystrokes data to the perpetrators and abusers of the crime syndicate. Once the crime syndicate gets illegal access of the first key component of an individual's communication channel, that person controls what the person receives in its mailbox and what it can send out. In essence, since the crime syndicate group has no interest that the targeted person communicates in her or his own will, with the absolute control of digital channels, they control information and can sabotage a good name of such an individual. If the real person is not informed of invitations to events, lectures, etc. and the crime syndicate is, they can produce a forged ID document and sent a non real person to such events for spying purposes and infiltrating into the networks of their interest, where they have no business to be, acting out relationships, that do not exist. Such individuals get infiltrated for the purposes of obtaining a know how on operations to sabotage and protect the ill segmented crime syndicate.

Second communication channel is a phone number. The real person can naively have a phone number thinking she or he is the only user of it. However, sim card cloning facilitates the incoming phone call redirect. Next step of incoming call diverts is the abuse of cell towers where the sim card connects to. Once the crime syndicate has access to those, they can block and redirect the communication from the victim and respond to phone calls in such method, that the victim does not have any idea the call was ever registered on their device, missing important meetings, job opportunities, events, friend's invitations, etc. Not only hijacking of incoming phone calls and text messages, but also producing false digital connections, that a person is talking to somebody else.

Physical access and control of the victim

In order for the crime syndicate to operate in incognito mode behind the individual's back, they need to have complete control of her's or his living habitat. In this particular case, a victim has created an office in a small coastal town in a house, where there are two entrances into the apartment. A back door and a front door, where at the neighbor's house is a camera directly set to the door of the victim, controlling her arrivals and departures from the premise. The criminal knows exactly where his victim is and had the permission from the owners of the premise to access the apartment. Even though the apartment is not on victim's name, her items are her property and the criminal had never obtained her permission to use her belongings nor was ever given a key by her nor a real signature for such access. In order to prove his cooperation with her, the criminal (narcissistic psychopath) used unethical methods to control her. First, to discredit her credibility, the psychiatric system was used to falsify a mental diagnosis that she never had. In the realm of police force, security field and the military, once such a diagnosis is given to an individual, they no longer have any real credibility of their statements. Since the criminal was well aware of such a fact, medical doctors, lawyers and judges were corrupt to follow up with his narrative, incapacitating the talents and physical capabilities of the person, each time she was not compliant with his manipulation around the world. When the victim was out of the house, the representatives of the crime syndicate accessed her premises and used different chemicals to manipulate with her physical appearance, organs, the brain, hair, skin, ect. Due to the reason that the high profile person of interest spread her information and showed her presence in many different institutions, the world know she exists, and cannot be eliminated, since a human body to discharge, becomes expensive. Next possible technique of a human destruction is through food remedies to control sleep patterns and other biological processes within a human body. Once the victim is in a stable place, the phases explained above, can easily be implemented in a small coastal town.

Methods of intimidation and control

To be efficient in intimidating and controlling a targeted person by the crime syndicates, the first step is a take over of communication channels of such a high profile individual. Once a complete take over of communication is established (mobile phone and e-mails) any attempt of a skilled and educated individual to obtain a honest job is in the control of the crime syndicates. They leave no free will of choice to the target to choose his or her path to elaborate on the talents that they have, but they are controlled and conditions by the one's having control of their communication. To bypass security measures of physical security key bypass, the person needs to be sedated in order for the non trusted criminal to obtain access to the communication channels. Once the person wakes up, realizing that he or she was sedated, realizes that the surroundings have changed and key components of security measures have been breached. The non-trusted criminal uses well trained personnel to obtain information from the victim and her intents of what are the next steps. Knowing court case numbers, names of prosecutors, protocol numbers of the law enforcement channels, the criminal, having access to digital communication and precise secret information, can forge and manipulate anything, especially, the official personnel in most inhumane and unethical methods. To recapitulate on the perfect crime, once a person is labeled 'mentally ill', such serious and organized crimes done by the crime syndicates who are even in hold of a forged ID, are possible, since such person is throughout the legal channels, being invalidated.

This concludes part one of the working paper, part two will elaborate more on technical administrative details on how high level crime syndicates operate.